

Biodiversity of East Asia in Steppe Ukraine: Collection of the genus *Chaenomeles* in the Botanical Garden of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine)

Kabar Anatoliy, Khromykh Nina, Didur Oleh
Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine)

➤ **Systematic description of the genus *Chaenomeles***

Scientific name: *Chaenomeles* Lindl. (from the Greek "split apple").

Taxonomy: Belongs to the family *Rosaceae* Juss., subfamily *Amygdaloideae*.

History of the name: Previously, the plants were known as "Japanese pear" (*Pyrus japonica*) or "Japanese quince" (*Cydonia japonica*), until John Lindley separated them into an independent genus in 1822.

➤ **Origin and composition**

Area: Naturally distributed in East Asia (China, Japan, Korea).

Natural species: The genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. includes five main species: *Ch. japonica*, *Ch. sinensis*, *Ch. speciosa* (endemic to China), *Ch. thibetica*, and *Ch. cathayensis*.

Hybrid forms: As a result of selection, taxa *Ch.* × *superba*, *Ch.* × *clarkiana*, *Ch.* × *vilmoriniana*, and *Ch.* × *californica* were obtained.

➤ **Ecological and morphological features (general characteristics)**

Life form: Deciduous or semi-evergreen shrubs (1–6 m tall), sometimes small trees.

Shoots: Often have thorns.

Flowers: Large (3–5 cm), solitary or in racemes of 2–6. Color varies from white or pink to scarlet red.

Root system: Powerful taproot, which ensures existence in arid conditions.

Fruits: Pear-shaped or apple-shaped, fragrant, ripen in September–October.

Environmental sustainability: High adaptability to the conditions of the steppe climate of Ukraine.

➤ ***Chaenomeles* Lindl. genus in the collection of DNU Botanical Garden**

The Botanical Garden of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University possesses a complete taxonomic the genus *Chaenomeles* collection, which was founded back in 1997 (Figure 1):

***Ch. japonica*:** Shrub 0.6–1.2 m tall, with the red-orange flowers.

***Ch. cathayensis*:** Plants can reach 6 m tall, and has large fragrant fruits (up to 7 cm long).

***Ch. speciosa*:** A fast-growing and long-lived species, whose fruits are used in food and medicine.

Hybrids: *Ch.* × *superba* and *Ch.* × *californica*, which combine the decorative qualities of the parent species.

➤ **Practical significance of the genus *Chaenomeles* plants**

Decorative: in landscape design for decorating the territory due to abundant flowering, and use to create green fences.

Medical and food: The fruits are rich in biologically active compounds, have confirmed antimicrobial activity.

Ch. japonica

Ch. cathayensis

Ch. speciosa

Ch. x superba

Ch. x californica

Figure 1. *Chaenomeles* Lindl. genus representatives in the Botanical Garden of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University

Due to their high content of organic acids and pectins, as well as an intense aroma, *Chaenomeles* fruits have a wide range of applications. These include complex industrial processing, confectionery and beverage production, and fruit preservation (such as the manufacturing of jellies, marmalades, jams, and candied fruits), while their dried slices are widely utilized as a fragrant additive to tea.

The presence of cuticular waxes on the skin of the fruits ensures their long shelf life, which allows the raw materials to be transported and processed for a long time after harvest.